

NECESSARY CONDITIONS FOR THE DESIGN OF CONTROL SYSTEMS
WITH OPTIMAL DISTURBANCE REJECTION

M. B. Subrahmanyam

Flight Control, Code 6012
Naval Air Development Center
Warminster, PA 18974-5000

ABSTRACT

Disturbance rejection is an important factor in the synthesis of controllers for several practical systems. In this paper we derive necessary conditions which need to be satisfied by the controller which yields maximum disturbance rejection. These conditions are useful in the synthesis of a controller which maximizes the disturbance rejection capacity of the system. The problem considered has connections to the H_∞ control theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem considered in the first three sections is stated below. The system is described by

$\dot{x} = A(t)x + B(t)u + G(t)v$, $x(t_0) = 0$, (1)
where $x(t)$, $u(t)$, $v(t)$ represent the system state, control, and disturbance input respectively. Let the feed back controller be given by

$$u(t) = C(t)x(t). \quad (2)$$

For a given $C(t)$ in (2), let $v(t)$ be chosen such that the performance index

$$J(v) = \frac{\int_{t_0}^T v'(t)R(t)v(t) dt}{\int_{t_0}^T \{x'(t)Q_1(t)x(t) + u'(t)Q_2(t)u(t)\} dt} \quad (3)$$

is minimized. Note that the superscript * denotes transpose of a matrix or a vector. In (3) $R(t) > 0$, $Q_1 \geq 0$ and $Q_2 \geq 0$. Let $\lambda = \inf J(v)$. Thus $v(t)$ which minimizes (3) represents the worst disturbance and λ gives the disturbance rejection capacity of the controller given by (2). The problem is to choose $C(t)$ which stabilizes (1) and maximizes λ .

It can be observed that the proposed problem has connections to the H_∞ optimal control theory. The novel features are that we consider time varying systems and in our case the interval of control is finite.

2. NECESSARY CONDITIONS FOR A FIXED $C(t)$

The equations (1)-(3) become

$$\dot{x} = (A(t) + B(t)C(t))x(t) + G(t)v(t), \quad (4)$$

$$x(t_0) = 0,$$

and

$$J(v) = \frac{\int_{t_0}^T v'(t)R(t)v(t) dt}{\int_{t_0}^T x'(t) \{Q_1(t) + C'(t)Q_2(t)C(t)\} x(t) dt} \quad (5)$$

The problem in this section is to choose $v(t)$ such that (5) is minimized.

Control problems in which the performance index is of the form of a quotient of definite integrals have been considered in [1-3]. We now state the conditions that are satisfied by $v(t)$ which minimizes (5).

Theorem 1. Consider the system given by (4) and (5). If $(x_0(t), v_0(t))$ minimizes (5), then there exists a nonzero $\psi_0(t)$ such that

$$\frac{d\psi_0}{dt} = -(A+BC)' \psi_0(t) - \lambda W x_0(t), \quad \psi_0(T) = 0, \quad (6)$$

where

$$W(t) = Q_1(t) + C'(t)Q_2(t)C(t), \quad (7)$$

$$\lambda = \inf \frac{\int_{t_0}^T v'(t)R(t)v(t) dt}{\int_{t_0}^T x'(t)W(t)x(t) dt}, \quad (8)$$

and

$$v_0(t) = R^{-1}(t)G'(t)\psi_0(t). \quad (9)$$

Thus we have a two-point boundary value problem given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_0 \\ \dot{\psi}_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A + BC & GR^{-1}G' \\ -\lambda W(t) & -(A+BC)' \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ \psi_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

with

$$x_0(t_0) = 0, \quad \psi_0(T) = 0. \quad (11)$$

It can be deduced from the following theorem that the minimum value of (5) is given by the smallest positive value of λ for which the boundary value problem given by (10) and (11) has a solution with

$$\int_{t_0}^T x'(t)W(t)x(t) dt > 0.$$

Theorem 2: Let (x, ψ) satisfy the boundary value problem

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A + BC & GR^{-1}G' \\ -\lambda W(t) & -(A+BC)' \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \psi \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

$$x(t_0) = 0, \quad \psi(T) = 0, \quad (13)$$

for some λ such that $\int_{t_0}^T x'Wx dt > 0$. Also

let $v \triangleq R^{-1}G'\psi$. Then

$$\frac{\int_{t_0}^T v'(t)R(t)v(t) dt}{\int_{t_0}^T x'(t)W(t)x(t) dt} = \lambda. \quad (14)$$

3. A NECESSARY CONDITION FOR λ_{\max}

We assume that there is a $C_0(t)$ which maximizes λ and stabilizes the system. Also assume that $C_0(t)$ has a neighborhood in which the system maintains stability. To derive the necessary condition of this section, the procedure of Refs. [4] and [5] can be followed. Now the necessary condition satisfied by $C_0(t)$ can be stated as follows:

Theorem 3: Consider the boundary value problem

$$\dot{x}_0 = (A+BC)x_0 + GR^{-1}G^*\psi_0, \quad (15a)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_0 = -(A+BC)^*\psi_0 - \lambda Wx_0 \quad (15b)$$

with

$$x_0(t_0)=0, \quad \psi_0(T)=0. \quad (16)$$

Let $C_0(t)$ maximize the minimum positive value of λ for which (15) and (16) have a solution with $\int_{t_0}^T x_0^* W x_0 dt > 0$. Denote the value of λ corresponding to $C_0(t)$ by λ_0 . Let $\delta C(t)$ denote an elemental perturbation of $C_0(t)$. Then $C_0(t)$ satisfies

$$\int_{t_0}^T (\psi_0^* B(t) + \lambda_0 x_0^* C_0^*(t) Q_2(t)) \delta C(t) x_0(t) dt = 0.$$

4. OBSERVER-BASED CONTROLLER PROBLEM

The system equations are given by

$$\dot{x} = A(t)x + B(t)u + G(t)v, \quad x(t_0) = 0, \quad (17)$$

$$y = C_2(t)x, \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = A(t)\hat{x} + B(t)u + L(t)[C_2x - C_2\hat{x}], \quad \hat{x}(t_0) = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$u = C(t)\hat{x}, \quad (20)$$

where $y(t)$ denotes the output vector and \hat{x} , the observer state. Assume that the observer gain $L(t)$ is given. For a given $C(t)$, let λ denote the minimum value of the performance index

$$J(v) = \frac{\int_{t_0}^T v^* R v dt}{\int_{t_0}^T (x^* Q_1 x + u^* Q_2 u) dt}. \quad (21)$$

For maximal disturbance rejection, we need to choose $C(t)$ such that λ is maximized.

The above equations can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{\hat{x}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B & C \\ LC_2 & A+BC-LC_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \hat{x} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} G \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} v, \quad (22)$$

$$x(t_0) = \hat{x}(t_0) = 0, \quad (23)$$

with the performance index being

$$J(v) = \frac{\int_{t_0}^T v^* R v dt}{\int_{t_0}^T \begin{pmatrix} x^* & \hat{x}^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Q_1 & 0 \\ 0 & C^* Q_2 C \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ \hat{x} \end{pmatrix} dt}. \quad (24)$$

For fixed $C(t)$, if $v(t)$ minimizes (24), then it also minimizes the alternate cost functional

$$J_1(v) = \frac{\Delta}{2} \int_{t_0}^T (v^* R v - \lambda (x^* Q_1 x + \hat{x}^* C^* Q_2 C \hat{x})) dt \quad (25)$$

where λ is the minimum value of (24). The necessary conditions for optimal $v(t)$ can be stated as follows:

Theorem 4: Consider the system given by (17)-(20) for fixed $C(t)$ with the cost functional given by (21). If $v(t)$ minimizes (21), then there exist adjoint vectors $\psi(t)$ and $\hat{\psi}(t)$, not both identically zero, such that

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = -A^*\psi - (LC_2)^*\hat{\psi} - \lambda Q_1 x \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{d\hat{\psi}}{dt} = -(BC)^*\psi - (A+BC-LC_2)^*\hat{\psi} - \lambda C^* Q_2 C \hat{x} \quad (27)$$

$$\psi(T) = \hat{\psi}(T) = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$v(t) = R^{-1}(t)G^*(t)\psi(t) \quad (29)$$

where λ is the minimum value of (21).

Thus we have a two-point boundary value problem given by (22), (23), and (26)-(29). As in Section 2, it can be shown that the minimum value of (21) is the least positive λ for which the boundary value problem has a solution with $\int_{t_0}^T (x^* Q_1 x + \hat{x}^* C^* Q_2 C \hat{x}) dt > 0$.

Finally, we note that as in Section 3, a necessary condition satisfied by $C(t)$ which maximizes λ can be derived.

REFERENCES

- [1] Subrahmanyam, M. B., "Necessary conditions for minimum in problems with nonstandard cost functionals," *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, Vol. 60, No. 3, 1977, pp. 601-616.
- [2] Subrahmanyam, M. B., "On integral inequalities associated with a linear operator equation," *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, Vol. 92, No. 3, 1984, pp. 342-346.
- [3] Subrahmanyam, M. B., "On applications of control theory to integral inequalities: II," *SIAM Journal on Control and Optimization*, Vol. 19, No. 4, 1981, pp. 479-489.
- [4] Bratus, A. S. and Seiranyan, A. P., "Sufficient conditions for an extremum in eigenvalue optimization problems," *PMM U.S.S.R. (Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics, English translation)*, Vol. 48, No. 4, 1984, pp. 466-474.
- [5] Tadjbakhsh, I. and Keller, J. B., "Strongest columns and isoperimetric inequalities for eigenvalues," *ASME Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 29, No. 1, 1962, pp. 159-164.